

PSYCHOLOGICAL TOURISM AS A WAY TO RESOLVE INTERNAL CONFLICTS

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Annotation. *The concept of psychological tourism combines the aspects of psychotherapeutic tourism and tourism with a psychological component, focusing on organized recreation and professional therapy to restore the "self" through healing environments and physical challenges. This type of tourism promotes self-reflection and the re-evaluation of personal experiences, helping individuals work through internal conflicts and reconnect with their cultural and geographical identity. An empirical study involving 125 respondents examined the influence of climate and landscape preferences on psychological tourism choices, revealing that individuals who feel disconnected from their cultural or environmental roots tend to choose exotic and extreme tours. Psychological tourism thus facilitates personal growth by fostering a deep engagement with the present moment and allowing individuals to reconnect with their identity and values.*

Key words: Psychological tourism, Internal conflicts, Psychotherapy, Cultural identity, Ethnofunctional psychotherapy, Gestalt therapy, Ethnic identity, Personal growth, Landscape therapy, Motivational consistency.

Абстрактный. Концепция психологического туризма объединяет аспекты психотерапевтического туризма и туризма с психологической составляющей, сосредотачиваясь на организованном отдыхе и профессиональной терапии для восстановления «я» через исцеляющую природу и физические испытания. Этот вид туризма способствует саморефлексии и переоценке личного опыта, помогая людям работать с внутренними конфликтами и восстанавливать связь со своей культурной и географической идентичностью. В исследовании с участием 125 респондентов был изучен выбор климатических и ландшафтных предпочтений для психологического туризма, который показал, что те, кто чувствует разобщенность со своими корнями, предпочитают экзотические и экстремальные туры. Таким образом, психологический туризм способствует личностному росту, вовлекая в глубокое осознание настоящего момента и позволяя людям воссоединиться со своей идентичностью и ценностями.

Ключевые слова: Психологический туризм, Внутренние конфликты, Психотерапия, Культурная идентичность, Этнофункциональная психотерапия, Гештальт-терапия, Этническая идентичность, Личностный рост, Ландшафтная терапия, Мотивационная согласованность.

Annotatsiya. Psixologik turizm kontseptsiyasi psixoterapevtik turizm va psixologik tarkibga ega bo'lgan turizmni o'zida mujassam etib, davolovchi muhit va jismoniy sinovlar orqali "men" ni tiklash uchun uyushtirilgan dam olish va professional terapiyaga e'tibor qaratadi. Ushbu turizm turi shaxsiy tajribalarni qayta baholash va o'z-o'zini aks ettirishga yordam beradi, shaxslarni ichki nizolarini ishlashga va o'zlarining madaniy va geografik identitetini tiklashga undaydi. 125 nafar respondentni o'z ichiga olgan empirik tadqiqot shuni ko'rsatdiki, o'z madaniy yoki atrof-muhit ildizlari bilan aloqasi yo'qolgan shaxslar ekzotik va ekstremal turlarni afzal ko'rishadi. Shu tariqa, psixologik turizm shaxsiy o'sishga hissa qo'shadi va insonlarni o'z identiteti va qadriyatlarini bilan qayta bog'lanishga imkon beradi.

Kalit so‘zlar: Psixologik turizm, Ichki nizolar, Psixoterapiya, Madaniy identitet, Etnofunksional psixoterapiya, Gestalt terapiya, Etnik identitet, Shaxsiy o‘shish, Landshaft terapiyasi, Motivatsion uyg‘unlik.

The emergence of psychological tourism as a separate tourist practice, in general, actualized the topic of interaction between psychology and tourism in the scientific community. In most works, this problem is most often reduced to two applied aspects: either to the psychological factors of consumerism in tourism, or to the analysis of tourism as a situation of challenges of the eco-environment in relation to the individual. The emerging need for psychological tourism and psychological tourism itself as a phenomenon require, in our opinion, theoretical understanding from the position of its correctional and therapeutic potential, contribution to personal development and self-improvement. Psychological tourism as a concept combines two alternative directions: psychotherapeutic tourism and tourism with the involvement of a psychological component. Both directions put at the forefront the problem of combining organized recreation and professional psychotherapy, original recovery technologies in the conditions of healing resources of nature and adequate extreme sports, which restore the psychological and spiritual reserves of the "I". From this point of view, psychological tourism is an existential event for the individual, fundamentally changing its bio-psycho-socio-spiritual nature. Psychological tourism involves re-evaluation of personal experience, working through internal conflicts, restoration of ethnic, landscape-geographical, cultural identity of a person.

When organizing psychological tours, it is important to select a psychotherapeutic program and technologies based on the psychological problems of clients, some of which can be realized in the form of a potential request from the client, while some can be in the field of internal conflicts that are unconscious to him. This problem prompted us to conduct a study of the possibilities of using psychological diagnostic methods when selecting psychological tourism practice, taking into account existing ethnofunctional discrepancies and internal conflicts of the individual associated with his value orientations. Three basic principles of Gestalt therapy correspond to the methodological essence of psychological tourism: the principle of concentration on the present as opposed to the past and future, the principle of active participation of the client in therapy, expressed in the continuous search for new psychological ways out of the problem, and the principle of a comprehensive understanding of a person in the unity of the psychological and physical. Psychological tourism can provide Gestalt therapy with the best opportunities for implementing these principles in practice. Tourism as a social practice offers the subject, literally, an exit from the environment familiar to him, establishing new boundaries of contact with the outside world.

Tourism offers a reorganization of the individual experience of the subject, familiarization with new values and meanings. Tourism initiates new gestalts to replace the outdated ones that hinder the development of the individual. Tourism becomes a subject of an organized axiospatial space — a part of the social environment, specially organized for the positive dynamics of the individual. Psychological tourism gives a person the opportunity to exist “here and now”, sometimes breaking the connection with the past and the future, immersing the individual in a new reality for him. “Reality” is a key metaphor of gestalt therapeutic practice, forcing a person to perceive the situation as a given.

Tourism provides a person with situations in which he can truly feel his being, detaching himself from the past and not looking into the future, flexibly regulate the contact difference when meeting with other objects and subjects of the environment. Thus, the experimental-

phenomenological approach of Gestalt therapy is perfectly supported by the concept of psychological tourism, encouraging the subject to independently conduct a psychological experiment and observe the emerging phenomena. One of the most important requirements of Gestalt therapy is the recording of observed phenomena by the client himself, which generates in him awareness of his mental impulses. Therefore, one of the most important elements of psychological tourism is the constant reflection of the subject of feelings, emotions, spontaneous patterns of behavior that arise during a tourist trip, which can be provided by a specialist psychotherapist. The most important, from a psychotherapeutic point of view, personal acquisition of tourism is the opportunity to restore internal consistency. This concerns the motivational-value sphere, as well as the ethnocultural identity of the individual. We see the existential meaning of tourist practices in the fact that through the knowledge of other cultural worlds, a person returns to the origins of his own culture, overcomes his cultural marginality in the modern world, feeling a commitment to a set of values, beliefs, and symbols associated with his own cultural tradition.

The subject's existential experience is based on a person's specific understanding of not only the world, but also of himself. "In the process of metapersonal self-interpretation, a person understands that his essence can be understood by turning his gaze not only inward, but also at the psychological characteristics of other people, society and the universe." Mastering one's nature, maturing to the ability to make choices and understanding one's freedom is possible only with "the ability of the individual to renounce the world with which he has grown together," to go beyond the limits of his own Self, in the conditions of transition to a state of new beingness of the individual, to getting rid of "dead" gestalts.

Quite indicative in this regard is the theory of working through ethnofunctional discrepancies in the human psyche, on the basis of which a corresponding technique has emerged that has successfully proven itself in the psychotherapy of depressive spectrum disorders. Ethnofunctional psychotherapy should consist of increasing the degree of integrity of the system of ethnofunctional relations of a person, in increasing the level of his mental adaptation. The result of ethnofunctional psychotherapy is the restoration of the integrity of the ethnoid - a subjectively preferred image of ethnic identification of the individual. The priority factor in the process of development of the ethnoid is the attitude of a person to a group of climatic and geographical features, which directly leads to the idea of tourism as a powerful means of climatic and landscape psychotherapy. Numerous domestic and foreign studies show that a person's attitude to the natural environment of his birth and residence is a priority factor in his mental ontogenesis. Based on these ideas, a hypothesis arose about the specificity of preferences when choosing various aspects of psychological tourism practice among ethnofunctionally-coordinated and ethnofunctionally-discoordinated subjects in relation to climatic and geographical features.

The methodological basis of the study was formed by psychoanalytic, existential approaches associated in gestalt therapy, ecological and ethnofunctional psychology and psychotherapy, value-oriented approach in psychology and psychodiagnostics of internal conflicts of the individual. The main empirical method of the study was a survey, including the diagnostic technique "Level of the relationship between "Value" and "Availability" in various spheres of life" aimed at identifying discrepancies and disintegration in the motivational and personal sphere; a technique for identifying the severity of emotional attitudes to groups of ethnic characteristics, which allows identifying the degree of ethnofunctional consistency of the subject in relation to landscape and climatic characteristics, as well as the author's questionnaire on psychological tourism, in which the key aspects were the choice of the region and the concept of the psychological tour. Non-parametric criteria and non-linear correlation were used to assess the

reliability of the research results. The study sample consisted of 125 people. The survey involved 67 women and 58 men.

Based on the additive projective method of identifying the severity of emotional attitudes to groups of ethnic characteristics, two groups of respondents were identified, who had either an emotionally positive attitude or an emotionally negative attitude to a complex of climatic and geographical characteristics of the place of residence. The assignment to one of the groups was based on the analysis of open-ended answers of the respondents, representing the completion of sentences (for example: I think that the area in which I live...; I think that the climate in which I live... etc.). Representatives of the first group, ethnofunctionally-coordinated respondents, predominantly gave emotionally positive answers (for example: "I think that the area in which I live... is optimal; "I think that the climate in which I live... suits me"). This group of respondents consisted of 66 people. The respondents of the second group, 59 respondents, had a negative emotional attitude to some extent towards the landscape and climate characteristics of their own place of residence ("I think that the area in which I live is not to my liking..."; "I think that the climate in which I live is harsh, unfavorable...").

The analysis of the ratio of the answers of ethnofunctionally-coordinated and ethnofunctionally-incoordinated respondents regarding the climatic and geographical region of the psychological tour revealed significant differences in their preferences. The subjects with a coordinated ethnoid regarding the climatic and geographical characteristics more often preferred the landscape and climate of their original place of residence as a place for the psychological tour. On the contrary, for the majority of subjects with an ethnoid incoordinated regarding the climatic and geographical characteristics, the choice of an exotic landscape and climate turned out to be preferable. From the standpoint of ethnofunctional psychodiagnostics and psychotherapy, the inconsistency of sociocultural and anthropo-biological ethnic characteristics of a person with the landscape and climatic conditions of his birth and residence is a marker of the deepening of the nosological attribution of depressive disorders. Since the essence of ethnofunctional psychotherapy consists of increasing the degree of coherence of the personality ethnoid (subjectively preferred image of ethnic identification), it is obvious that the therapeutic task of psychotourism for people with ethnofunctional discrepancies is to work through their relationship to the natural environment in order to understand the disrupted connections with the climatic, geographical and landscape conditions of their "native" region of habitation.

The analysis of the tourist services market in the psychological tourism sector showed that the following types of tourism most often fall into the category of psychological tours: eco-tourism, agro-tourism, jailoo-tourism, extreme tourism, tourism with comprehension of foreign cultural spiritual practices. A significant relationship was found between ethnofunctional mismatch and the choice of foreign cultural spiritual practices and extreme types of tourism. Ethnofunctionally mismatched subjects showed a high percentage of preferences in the area of choosing a psychological tour associated with comprehension of foreign cultural spiritual practices. Craving for a foreign cultural environment, for foreign traditions, especially in the spiritual sphere, is a characteristic sign of a crisis of ethnic identity of an individual, accompanying the moral marginality of the subject in the conditions of ethnocultural uncertainty, partly destructive behavior and a different spectrum of depressive disorders.

Ethnofunctionally misaligned subjects significantly more often chose the extreme tour concept for themselves. For psychological tourism specialists, manifestations of a craving for an extreme concept of tour organization, as a pursuit of thrills, may indicate the presence of internal personality conflicts associated with unconscious discrepancies in the area of ethnic identification.

The differences we identified in the preferences for the type of psychological tourism among the two categories of subjects indicate the need to analyze potential internal conflicts among ethnofunctionally discordant subjects when organizing psychological tours.

Subjects with ethnofunctional discrepancies in the complex of landscape-climatic features confirm by their choice of psychological tourist practice the existence of a crisis in ethnic identification, unconscious internal conflicts related to the cultural and geographical environment of the region of residence. The task of psychological tours is also the restoration of the internal axiological consistency of the individual.

The existing contradictions in the motivational sphere when choosing psychological tourism practice, in our opinion, can become a significant subject for the analysis of the psychotherapeutic component of the psychological tour program.

Conclusion

1. It has been established that psychological tourism can act as a tool for resolving internal conflicts of the individual, a factor in consolidating the ethnic, landscape-geographical and cultural identity of a person.

2. The significance of the methodology of ethnofunctional psychotherapeutic practice and the need for its application in the system of organizing psychotours have been empirically proven.

3. Unconscious contradictions by clients in the aspect of conscious motivational choice of cognitive and eco-oriented practice of psychological tourism and its unconscious denial have been revealed.

Taken together, the obtained results open up new possibilities for the strategy and tactics of psychotherapeutic work in psychological tourism.

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